

Local stresses in crane runway girders near transverse stiffeners Experimental and numerical investigations

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ABSTRACT

In practice, crane runway girders are typically designed with additional transverse stiffeners to improve the buckling resistance of the web and to prevent rotation of the top flange due to eccentric introduction of the vertical wheel loads. This leads to an increase in local vertical stresses in the area of the welds between the transverse stiffener, the web and the top flange. The actual stress field has not yet been researched in detail and is therefore unknown. However, the local stresses have a significant impact on the fatigue design of the crane runway beam and the required girder dimensions. Therefore, this paper sets out to investigate the local stress field in detail. For this purpose, several laboratory tests are carried out on a crane runway girder with crane rail for heavy duty cranes. The vertical wheel loading is applied on the crane rail at different positions near transverse stiffeners, including concentric and eccentric position of the load at the rail. Tests are carried out with and without elastomeric bearing pad beneath the crane rail. The strains in the web and the stiffeners are measured by means of 40 strain gauges. The results of the experimental tests are used to calibrate a numerical finite element model. Thereby it is possible to investigate the whole stress field near transverse stiffeners, also in regions without measuring devices. Based on the investigations described in this study, several observations and conclusions can be made with respect to an improved fatigue verification. Thus, an initial basis is created for designing crane runway beams with transverse stiffeners that are both safer and more resource-efficient in the future.

Keywords: crane runway girder, transverse stiffener, local stresses

1 INTRODUCTION

Transverse stiffeners in crane runway girders are crucial near the supports to transfer the loads from the girder to the supporting structure. In the case of welded crane runway girders with greater web heights, the arrangement of additional transverse stiffeners between the supports also improves the buckling load-bearing capacity of the web and prevents twisting of the top flange due to eccentric wheel load introduction. In EN 1993-6 (1) there are currently no rules for calculating the local stresses in the connection areas between the transverse stiffeners and the top flange and no reference to the influence of the transverse stiffeners on the stresses in the web plate around the stiffener is given. For crane runway girders made of hot-rolled sections (typically used for light crane operation) and no cut-out in the transverse stiffeners, a theoretically derived model for fatigue design was developed by Euler and Kuhlmann in (2). This model should be validated by experimental investigations in the future. Welded crane runway girders composed of individual plates are generally used for medium to heavy crane operation and are usually designed with cut-outs in the transverse stiffeners in the region of the web-top flange or web-bottom flange connections.

Preliminary numerical investigations have shown that transverse stiffeners with such cut-outs lead to a significant change of the local stress field. Both Maas (3) and Demo and Fisher (4) have reported cracks in welds between the transverse stiffeners and the top flange or in welds between the transverse stiffeners and the web (at the ends of the cut-outs).

This paper investigates the actual stress field around the transverse stiffeners in detail. Both laboratory tests and numerical calculations are carried out and the results are presented in the following sections.

2 LABORATORY TESTS

Laboratory tests were carried out on a used crane runway girder including crane rail and elastomeric bearing pad. The girder had been replaced by a new girder during a refurbishment. The I-shaped cross-section had following dimensions: top flange (900×35mm), bottom flange (900×25mm), top flange lamella (630×30mm), bottom flange lamella (870×25mm) and web (2300×23mm). The crane rail of type A 120 is mounted on an elastomeric bearing pad with a thickness of 6 mm, reinforced with a steel sheet. On the original crane runway girder, transverse stiffeners were arranged at intervals of 2190 mm. The test girder, consisting of a part of the original girder, has a length of $L = 2400$ mm and has two L-shaped cross stiffeners (L 300/98/8) in the middle. The geometry of the test girder is shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Test girder with top flange lamella (girder 1) and test girder after removal of the top flange lamella (girder 1a)

In the test, the girder was supported by a flat steel bar, which was arranged over the entire length of the girder under the bottom chord lamella directly under the web plate. The flat steel bar was in full contact with the laboratory floor. Lateral support of the beam was ensured by additional wooden wedges and steel wedges, which were inserted between the bottom flange lamella and the laboratory floor. Additional numerical calculations confirmed that the investigated local stress field around the top edge of the transverse stiffeners was not influenced by this unrealistic continuous support of the bottom flange lamella in the test (compared to the support conditions of the crane runway girder with the global bending stress field).

The vertical compression load was applied via a spherical piston (radius $r = 40$ mm) on the top of the crane rail. The position of the crane runway girder in the test frame was varied for the different

tests so that different load positions (in both the longitudinal and transverse direction) could be investigated. The positions $x = 0$ (i.e. directly above the web plates of the transverse stiffeners) and $x = \pm 150$ mm were tested in longitudinal direction and $y = 0$ (i.e. directly above the web plate) and $y = \pm 30$ mm were tested in transverse direction. A total of 9 different load positions for the beam with top flange lamella and elastomeric bearing pad under the rail were investigated. To investigate the influence of the elastomeric bearing pad, additional 9 tests, with the same load positions, were carried out without elastomeric bearing pad. For this purpose, the pad was removed and the rail was placed directly on the top flange lamella.

To investigate the effect of the top flange lamella on the local stress field, it was removed after the first two test series. The test girder without top flange lamella, see *Fig. 1*, was also tested with the load positions described above (a total of 9 with and 9 without elastomeric bearing pad). For the results and descriptions in this paper, the test girder with top flange lamella (with and without elastomeric bearing pad) is referred to as girder 1 and the test girder without top flange lamella (also with and without elastomeric bearing pad) as girder 1a.

The local vertical strains ε_z were measured during the tests using strain gauges. A total of 22 strain gauges and 6 additional strain rosettes (3 strain gauges each) were applied to the transverse stiffeners and the web plate near the load application point, see *Fig. 2*. The upper row of strain gauges was used to measure the local strains at detail 1 (web-top flange connection) and was attached to the web plate 40 mm below the lower edge of the top flange in order to avoid unintended local influences of the weld between the upper edge of the web and the top flange on the measurement results. The lower strain gauge row had a distance of 80 mm to the lower edge of the upper flange. Here, the distribution of local strains was measured at detail 2 (transverse stiffener-girder web connection at the cut-out). The strain gauges were arranged in the longitudinal direction of the girder so that a total length of 300 mm of the web - symmetrical to the load application position - was covered. The strain gauges on the transverse stiffeners, for measuring the local strains at detail 3 (transverse stiffener-top chord connection), were fitted 30 mm below the lower edge of the top chord.

Fig. 2. Arrangement of the strain gauges and rosettes at the test girder

Fig. 3 shows the test girder with top flange lamella (girder 1) and the measuring device attached in the testing machine. The support situation on the flat steel bar in the axis of the web and the additional wedges under the outer edges of the bottom flange lamella are clearly visible. A total of 36 tests (= 9 load positions each for girders 1 and 1a, with and without elastic support) were carried out. The vertical compression load R was applied to the upper edge of the crane rail displacement-controlled. The piston with spherical head can also be seen in the picture. The load R was increased until the maximum strain in the strain gauges was approx. 1 ‰. This ensured a purely elastic behaviour without plastic effects, as it is the case for real crane operation. The measured strains returned to zero after the tests, which also indicates purely elastic behaviour.

Fig. 3. Test girder with top flange lamella (girder 1) in the testing machine and FE-model of girder 1

3 NUMERICAL SIMULATIONS OF THE TESTS

The numerical calculations were carried out with the software package Abaqus. The entire crane runway girder and the crane rail were modelled using quadratic solid elements of type C3D20R. The elastomeric bearing pad was modelled by means of a contact condition between the underside of the crane rail and the upper side of the crane runway girder, whereby the rail can be lifted freely (as in the test). The bedding stiffness parameter of the elastomeric bearing pad was assumed to be $c = 100 \text{ kN/cm}^3$, based on own empirical values for the material used. The numerical model includes the entire test girder with its length of 2400 mm, see Fig. 3. The selected mesh density resulted from a sensitivity study and from past experience with similar tests on crane runway girders. The material behaviour of steel was modelled as linear elastic. The modulus of elasticity and Poisson ratio were assumed as $E = 210\,000 \text{ N/mm}^2$ and $\nu = 0.3$, respectively. The result paths are identical in height to the position of the strain gauge rows at $z = 40$ and $z = 80$ mm on both sides of the beam web and at $z = 30$ mm on the transverse stiffeners, see Fig. 2.

The actual wear of the used crane rail ($a = 2$ mm) and its actual position on the top of the test girder (centred over the web plate) were considered in the FE-model in accordance with the measurements in the laboratory. The welds between the upper edge of the web and the upper flange are designed with full penetration. In the numerical model, the upper flange and web plate are rigidly connected to each other. This also applies to the welds between the transverse stiffeners and the upper flange or the transverse stiffener and the web plate (actually designed as double fillet welds). The main results of the numerical calculations are presented in the following section and compared with the strain measurements from the tests.

4 COMPARISON OF LOCAL VERTICAL STRAINS – TEST VS. FE-SIMULATION

Fig. 4 and Fig. 5 show a comparison of results of the finite element calculations and the laboratory tests for girder 1 (with top flange lamella and a wheel load of $R = 500 \text{ kN}$). The numerical values

are significantly higher than the measured values when assuming full contact between the top flange lamella and the top flange (black lines). For this reason, the numerical model also analysed the case with an unplanned gap between the lamella and the top flange, which was actually present on the test girder. The fact that even slight deviations from the flatness between the top flange, top flange lamella and crane rail have significant influence on the level of local strains and stresses has already been highlighted by the authors in similar tests in the past (5). This effect was considered in the numerical model under the assumption of a constant gap in the longitudinal direction of the girder, which has a simplified linear distribution in the transverse direction (symmetrically). In the web axis, the gap dimension is 1 mm and decreases to 0 mm towards the longitudinal edges of the top flange lamella. Fig. 4 shows the comparison of results for load application directly above the transverse stiffener ($x = 0$) and directly above the web (concentric wheel load application, $y = 0$, see Fig. 2). The top two graphs summarise the results in the web plate at $z = 40$ mm and $z = 80$ mm. The bottom graphs show the results in the transverse stiffeners. In contrast to the girder web, the gap between the lamella and the top chord of the girder leads to an increase in local strains.

Fig. 4. Comparison of results for test girder 1: position of wheel load $x = 0, y = 0, R = 500$ kN

The comparison between the measured values and the strain curves of the FE-calculations for the case with the gap considered (blue lines) shows good agreement. The measured strains with and without elastomeric bearing pad are approximately the same. In this case, the bedding behaviour is obviously dominated by the closing of the gap between the lamella and the top flange, see also

Fig. 6. As a result, there is a clear redistribution of the contact pressure even for the case without an elastomeric bearing pad. This behaviour is accurately reproduced and confirmed by the FE-calculations. In the numerical result curves without a gap (black lines), the effect of the local strain reduction with an elastomeric bearing pad (compared to the case without an elastomeric bearing pad) can be clearly seen. The favourable influence of the elastomeric bearing pad (reduction of the strains in the area of the upper edge of the web by approx. 25%) is comparable to the design equations in (1).

Fig. 5 summarises the results for an eccentric wheel load ($y = 30$ mm) directly above the webs of the transverse stiffeners ($x = 0$). The measured strains in the web on the load facing side ($y+$) are well described by the results of the FE-calculation with gap. The measured values on the less loaded web surface ($y-$) generally show slightly higher strains than the corresponding FE results with gap.

Fig. 5. Comparison of results for test girder 1: position of wheel load $x = 0, y = +30$ mm, $R = 500$ kN

The two diagrams for the web position $z = 40$ mm clearly show the higher bending component of the FE-results compared to the lower bending component of the measured values. Compared to the FE-results without gap, the influence of the elastomeric bearing pad for the case with gap is also very low for the eccentric load application (recognisable from the almost identical results as for the case without elastomeric bearing pad).

Fig. 6 illustrates the influence of the gap between the lamella and the top flange on the strains in the web plate. The wheel load – strain diagram (position of the concentric wheel load at $x = y = 0$) for

two specific strain gauge positions. The two selected strain gauges are located directly below the concentric wheel load on both sides of the web ($x = 0$, $y = \pm 11.5$ mm, $z = 40$ mm, strain gauge I and strain gauge II in Fig. 2). For the visualisation, the two measured values were averaged and displayed as the curve ‘Test’. The measured strain curve with increasing wheel load is compared with the FE-calculations with and without modelled gap. There is very good agreement between the measured curve and the numerical results with gap for both the case with and without an elastomeric bearing pad. To summarise, it can be said that the presence of a local gap directly under the wheel load reduces the maximum local strains in the web plate and increases the local strains in the transverse stiffeners. It should be noted at this point that a constantly opening and closing gap leads to additional stress amplitudes in the welds between the top flange and the lamella, which in many cases cause premature fatigue cracks in this area.

Fig. 6. Wheel load-strain comparison for strain gauges I and II on the web plate at position $x = 0$, $y = \pm 11,5$ mm, $z = 40$ mm; girder 1 with position of wheel load at $x = y = 0$

Following the test series on crane runway girder with top flange lamella, the lamella was removed from the top flange. Subsequently, the same elastic tests (as previously on girder 1) were carried out on the resulting girder 1a without the top flange lamella.

Fig. 7 summarises the local vertical stress curves in the transverse stiffener and the web plate over the height for girder 1a without top flange lamella and without elastomeric bearing pad. The presented results are based on the FE-calculations carried out with concentric or eccentric wheel load ($y = 0$ or $y = +30$ mm, $R = 500$ kN) directly above the transverse stiffeners ($x = 0$). Fig. 7a shows the curves in the web plate of the girder, Fig. 7b those in the transverse stiffener. In addition to the numerical results, the measured values of the corresponding strain gauges are also presented. For this purpose, the measured strains were converted assuming a predominantly uniaxial stress state ($\sigma = E \cdot \varepsilon$). The vertical stresses in the web plate of the girder due to concentric wheel load decrease by approximately 15 % from the area of the upper edge of the web at $z = 15$ mm ($\sigma_{oz,1} = -73.8$ MPa) to the start of the transverse stiffener at $z = 100$ mm ($\sigma_{oz,2} = -62.8$ MPa). The corresponding stresses are used in the following section as reference stresses for details 1 and 2 under concentric wheel load. The positions $z = 15$ mm and $z = 100$ mm were selected as the stress-increasing effects towards the upper flange and the cut-out in the transverse stiffener web (shown in dotted lines) have largely subsided here.

The additional transverse bending stresses σ_T in the web plate due to eccentric wheel load application (shown in the second diagram of Fig. 7a) exhibit compressive stresses on the load facing side near the upper edge of the web and tensile stresses around the attachment point of the transverse stiffener. The zero crossing of the bending stresses can be determined at $z = 88$ mm. This vertical stress distribution of the bending stresses only occurs near the transverse stiffener ($x = 0$) and differs significantly from the decay behaviour of the web stresses for wheel loads at locations without transverse stiffeners. The superposition of the two vertical stress components $\sigma_{oz} \pm \sigma_T$

results in the decisive vertical stresses for detail 1 and detail 2 due to eccentric wheel load introduction $\sigma_{z,1} = -118.6$ MPa and $\sigma_{z,2} = -78.1$ MPa. The latter occurs on the load averted side. The vertical stresses σ_z for detail 2 (transverse stiffener-girder web connection at the cut-out) are smaller than for detail 1 (web-top flange connection). However, a worse construction detail must be considered for detail 2. Detail category 100 can be used for the welded-through weld between the web and the top flange, while detail category 63 should be used for the attachment point of the transverse stiffener at the web, see (6). Thus, in this case, detail 2 is decisive for the fatigue analysis compared to detail 1 (utilisation ratio detail 1 = $118.6/100 = 1.19 <$ utilisation ratio detail 2 = $78.1/63 = 1.24$).

Fig. 7. Distribution of vertical stresses over the height for girder 1a without elastomeric bearing pad and $R = 500$ kN at $x = 0$: a) stresses in girder web, b) stresses in web of transverse stiffener

The vertical stresses in the transverse stiffener are shown in Fig. 7b for three selected paths. Path 1 is located directly at the end of the cut-out. Paths 2 and 3 have a horizontal distance of 10 and 20 mm respectively. The measured values of the test are to be compared with the results of the FE-calculation for path 3. For the positions of the strain gauges or rosettes, see Fig. 2. The compressive stresses in the upper area of the transverse stiffener significantly increase near the cut-out. For positions $z \geq 50$ mm, the difference in vertical stresses in all three paths is negligibly small. The stresses of path 2 (distance of 10 mm from the cut-out) at a height of $z = 15$ mm are defined as the reference stresses for detail 3 (transverse stiffener-top chord connection, nominal stress approach). The corresponding vertical stresses for concentric and eccentric wheel load are therefore $\sigma_{oz,3} = -78.2$ MPa and $\sigma_{z,3} = -137.2$ MPa, respectively.

5 ESTIMATION OF THE FATIGUE EFFECT OF THE TRANSVERSE STIFFENER

The comparisons in the previous section have shown that the FE-model is able to reproduce the measured strains of the laboratory tests at the locations of the decisive fatigue verifications (details 1 to 3) with good approximation. This FE-model is therefore used to carry out additional FE-calculations on two virtual girders that have no transverse stiffeners near the wheel load introduction. The geometry of these girders corresponds to the dimensions of girders 1 and 1a. The following 6 models are investigated, and their results are compared with each other:

- model 1: girder 1a without top flange lamella, without elastomeric bearing pad
- model 2: girder 1a without top flange lamella, with elastomeric bearing pad
- model 3: girder 1 without elastomeric bearing pad, without gap between lamella and top flange
- model 4: girder 1 with elastomeric bearing pad, without gap between lamella and top flange
- model 5: girder 1 without elastomeric bearing pad, with gap between lamella and top flange
- model 6: girder 1 with elastomeric bearing pad, with gap between lamella and top flange

For each of these six models, a calculation was carried out with and without transverse stiffeners under the wheel load. In the reference case without transverse stiffeners under the wheel load, the load was applied in the middle between two transverse stiffeners, which had a distance of 2190 mm (as executed in the original crane runway girder). The distance between the transverse stiffeners has no influence on the web stresses from the concentric wheel load, but does influence the additional transverse bending stresses in the web plate from eccentric wheel load application. The comparison of the results with and without transverse stiffeners is carried out based on the utilization factor for the fatigue design check at the decisive points (details 1 to 3). In accordance with Eq. (1), reference is always made to detail 1 without transverse stiffeners under the wheel load.

$$\eta = \frac{\Delta\sigma_{z,i}/\Delta\sigma_{c,i}}{\Delta\sigma_{z,0}/\Delta\sigma_{c,0}} \quad (1)$$

where

$\Delta\sigma_{z,i}$ is the local vertical stress at the decisive construction detail (FE-result for detail $i = 1$ to 3),
 $\Delta\sigma_{c,i}$ is the fatigue resistance (in N/mm² at $N = 2 \cdot 10^6$ stress cycles) of the considered details according to (6), nominal stress approach ($\Delta\sigma_{c,1} = 100$, $\Delta\sigma_{c,2} = 63$, $\Delta\sigma_{c,3} = 50$),
 $\Delta\sigma_{z,0}$ is the local vertical stress on detail 1 without transverse stiffener (FE-result at $z = 15$ mm),
 $\Delta\sigma_{c,0}$ is the fatigue resistance for detail 1 without transverse stiffener: $\Delta\sigma_{c,0} = 100$ N/mm².

The following comparison of results considers concentric ($y = 0$) as well as eccentric wheel load ($y = 30$ mm), with $\Delta R = 500$ kN. The collected results are graphically summarized in Fig. 8. Related utilization ratios $\eta < 1.0$ mean that the fatigue check outside the transverse stiffener area remains decisive.

Fig. 8. Comparison of the utilisation factors of the fatigue checks in relation to the utilisation factors of the web-flange connection without transverse stiffener for a) detail 1, b) detail 2 and c) detail 3

Subsequently, the related utilization ratios η for model 1 and concentric wheel load are exemplarily calculated using Eq. (2). The numerically determined vertical stress near the web-top flange connection from centric wheel load between two transverse stiffeners is $\sigma_{oz,0} = 78.8$ N/mm² for model 1. With $\sigma_{oz,1} = 73.8$ N/mm² the comparison for detail 1 results in:

$$\eta_{\text{detail 1}} = \frac{73.8/100}{78.8/100} = 0.94 \quad (2)$$

The corresponding values for details 2 and 3 are calculated in Eqs. (3) and (4), with $\sigma_{oz,i}$ in Fig. 7.

$$\eta_{\text{detail 2}} = \frac{62.8/63}{78.8/100} = 1.26 \quad (3)$$

$$\eta_{\text{detail 3}} = \frac{78.2/50}{78.8/100} = 1.99 \quad (4)$$

The result values for detail 1 in *Fig. 8a* are all less than 1.0. The fatigue design check in the area between the transverse stiffeners would therefore be sufficient for the web-top flange welded connection, for the investigated model girders. For this purpose, equations for calculating the local stresses are available in EN 1993-6. These formulae are based on the investigations in (7-9).

The results in *Fig. 8b* show that detail 2 at the transverse stiffener is decisive for most fatigue design checks compared to detail 1 without transverse stiffeners. This means that in these cases, the sole fatigue check for detail 1 between the transverse stiffeners provides unsafe results. Until more comprehensive studies are available, the following conservative approach is recommended: The local vertical stresses at the top edge of the web according to EN 1993-6 (without the influence of transverse stiffeners) should serve as the basis of the fatigue verification of detail 2. However, the fatigue resistance should be taken as $\Delta\sigma_{c,2} = 63 \text{ N/mm}^2$.

The result values for detail 3 in *Fig. 8c* are all significantly greater than 1.0, despite the slightly underestimated local stresses (calculated values for $z = 15 \text{ mm}$). The verification of the fillet weld connections between the transverse stiffeners and the top flange is therefore clearly more decisive than the verification for the welded web-top flange connection without the influence of transverse stiffeners. The comparison in *Fig. 8c* was carried out for crack initiation in the weld root with $\Delta\sigma_{c,3} = 50 \text{ N/mm}^2$. The results show that for the models investigated, changing the connection from a fillet weld to a full penetration weld ($\Delta\sigma_{c,3} = 100 \text{ N/mm}^2$, considering crack initiation in the transverse stiffener at the weld toe) also leads to result values above 1.0. It is therefore not recommended to weld the transverse stiffeners directly to the top flange, but to bolt them to it using a top plate, for example. This means that potential cracks starting from the weld can at least not propagate into the top flange.

In summary, the results indicate that further investigations are necessary to be able to accurately predict the local stress field near transverse stiffeners.

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